

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL ECONOMY DEVELOPMENT IN THE PRESENT

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Annotation: the article considers the importance of innovation activities and the relevance of development.

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Today, the development of mankind in many ways is directly related to the intensities of the development of Information Technology.

At the end of the twentieth century, with the penetration of the internet into various spheres of public life, such terms as “electronic government”, “electronic commerce”, “digital economy” appeared.

The term “digital economy” was first mentioned in a lecture by Nicholas Negroponte, an American computer scientist who worked at the University of Massachusetts in 1995, dedicated his colleagues to the superiority of an economy based on modern information and communication technologies over the old economy.

Having many advantages over the traditional economy, the digital economy became popular in a short period of time, initially in developed countries, and then around the world.

The digital economy is a system of economic, social and cultural relations using digital technologies, an example of which are primarily online services, distance learning, electronic payments, the internet trade of goods and services.

Currently, among the “Digital” countries, the leaders are Norway, Sweden and Switzerland. Among the top-10 countries in this regard are the United States, Great Britain, Denmark, Finland, Singapore and South Korea.

It is noted that the digital economy will bring about incomparable changes in more than half of the current existing spheres. In particular, according to experts from the World Bank, an increase in the number of fast internet users by 10 per cent will allow the gross volume of national economies to increase by an average of 0.4-1.4 per cent annually.

The rate of growth of the digital economy in the world is almost 20 per cent per year. In developed countries, the share of the digital economy in gross domestic product reached 7 percent. They are now seeing a huge roar from the introduction of the digital economy. In particular, the United States exports digital services worth more than 400 billion US dollars a year. More than 5 percent of this state gross domestic product falls directly on the internet and information and telecommunication technologies. Until 2025 year, the US added 20 trillion from the digitization of industry. the dollar is expected to gain. Such economic efficiency and productivity, especially in the production of consumer goods (10,3 trillion. dollar), the automotive industry (3,8 trillion. dollars) and logistics (3,9 trillion. dollar) is highlighted to be high.

According to the results of various studies, the impact of the digital economy on the world economy is 15,5 percent. Almost 40 percent of the value-added created in the world information and communication technology sector and 75 percent of patents related to blockchain technologies correspond to the shares of the United States and the people's Republic of China.

In recent years, a number of measures have been taken to digitize the economy in our country. Practical work has already been launched in order to create conditions for the rapid development of modern information technologies, to ensure information security.

In particular, this year, 1 million broadband ports have been installed on the Internet, the total number of which has reached 3 million. In addition, 19 thousand kilometers of fiber optic communication lines are being built, its lines are being connected.

The permeability of the data transmission network has increased 2 times at the level of regional centers, and 4 times at the level of district centers. In order to expand the scale of the service, about 3 thousand mobile base stations have been installed, their total number has reached 29 thousand and its coverage has reached 97 percent in the population and 84 percent in the high-speed direction. In order to meet the needs of the population for broadband mobile services, more than 3 000 base stations have been modernized by the "Uzmobayl" branch of "Uzbektelecom" JSC.

To date, on the basis of the development of telecommunication networks, 71 percent of the existing 19 462 social sphere facilities, including 6 827 facilities from 10 154 public education institutions, 4 374 facilities from 5 781 preschool education institutions and 2 668 facilities from 3 524 health care facilities, have created the opportunity to use high-speed Internet services on the

In order to ensure the future digital development of the Republic, the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on approval of the Strategy” Digital Uzbekistan — 2030” and measures for its effective implementation ” was adopted.

With this decree, within the framework of digital transformation of territories and networks, a number of tasks were defined until 2022:

to reach the total length of fiber optic communication built throughout the Republic up to 70 thousand kilometers;

* to reach the level of the social object with high-speed Internet world information network up to 100 percent;

* to increase the level of coverage of population with broadband mobile communication network to 100 percent;

In its place, it should be noted that in the life of our country, some elements of the digital economy are already successfully operating. In particular, taking into account the mass transfer of documents and communications to digital media, access to electronic signatures, communication with the state is also transferred to electronic platforms.

International experience shows that today digital technologies are rapidly developing, mainly in the scientific community and the private sector. Therefore, it is necessary for the state to create a favorable ecosystem with the support of innovative projects and IT companies in these areas.

It is also worthwhile for the state to support modern methods of digital education in the field of supporting the innovative and digital ecosystem, to develop norms for effective regulation of innovative services, to facilitate the assimilation of new markets, and to take measures to mitigate the risks that arise in the deepening of technological processes.

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